

Abstract

Mapping the PS Area: New Scalp Acupuncture for Post-Viral Sensory Recovery.

Paula Sousa^{1,2*} , and António Moreira⁴.

¹ ICBAS – School of Medicine and Biomedical Sciences, University of Porto, Portugal;

² CBSin - Centre of Biosciences in Integrative Health, Porto, Portugal;

³ MIPA, Université de Nîmes, Nîmes, France;

⁴ CIDESD - Research Centre in Sports, Health and Human Development, Vila Real, Portugal.

* Correspondence: pasousa32@gmail.com

Abstract

Smell and taste disorders have gained significant clinical prominence following the COVID-19 pandemic. Anosmia, hyposmia, dysgeusia, and hypogeusia have emerged as some of the most prevalent and persistent post-viral sequelae. These sensory impairments substantially diminish quality of life, affecting nutritional habits, emotional well-being, and personal safety. Given that effective pharmacological treatments remain limited, there is an increasing interest in exploring complementary neuromodulatory interventions. Cranial acupuncture, specifically Zhu's Scalp Acupuncture (ZSA), is predicated on the functional correlations between specific scalp regions and their underlying cortical areas. While ZSA offers established protocols for various neurological and sensory conditions, a specific scalp area for the systematised treatment of taste disorders had not yet been defined. Drawing upon neuroanatomical principles and functional cortical mapping, this communication introduces a newly developed cranial acupuncture region: the PS Area. The PS Area was defined based on the presumed cortical projection of the gustatory sensory cortex, situated within the parietal opercular–insular network. Anatomically, this area is mapped on the scalp as a bilateral 1 cm² square, centred approximately 2.5 cm vertically above the apex of the ear. Although originally conceived to address gustatory dysfunction, preliminary clinical observations suggest concurrent therapeutic effects on olfactory perception.

Citation: Sousa P., Rodrigues J., Deus M., Pedrosa M., Parreira R., Pereira F., Machado J., Moreira A. Mapping the PS Area: New Scalp Acupuncture for Post-Viral Sensory Recovery. *Journal of Complementary Therapies in Health*. 2026;4(2) 10.5281/zenodo.19887482

Publisher's Note: IPTC stays neutral concerning jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2026 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Figure 1 – Functional areas of the external surface of the left cerebral cortex: 1 - PS Area; 2 – Pre-frontal cortex; 3 – motor cortex; 4 – sensory cortex; 5 cerebellum

Keywords: Anosmia, Dysgeusia, Hypogeusia, Craniopuncture, Gustatory and Olfactory Dysfunctions.

Acknowledgements: This work was presented at the 1st Scientific Seminars of Complementary Therapies in Health, on 26 September 2025.